

Modelling of Lightning First Short Stroke Current Waveform by Stepped or Nonlinear Capacitance Discharges

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Abstract—Due to the varying nature of lightning events, the wave shapes of the same type of lightning currents differ significantly. Typical descriptions of the wave shape in form of (multi) exponential approximations are aimed to provide handy equations to describe the energy turn over within the discharge channel. However, for considerations where the leader growth phase is of particular interest, these approximations may oversimplify the physical nature of the stepped downward and upward leader growth and its associated pre-discharge current. Further on, they assume an impressed discharge current instead of a cloud charge, which may not be appropriate for some cases. So, with the help of capacitive-resistive equivalent circuit diagrams, in which capacitances are switched or steadily increased, the temporal change of the electric field during the development of lightning leaders is simulated. Both discontinuous pre-growth in jerk steps or continuous steady pre-growth of leaders are considered here. As a result, the front part of lightning first short stroke impulse currents can be calculated in more detail either analytically or numerically.

Index Terms—Lightning short stroke current, unipolar non-oscillating waveform, equivalent circuit diagram, ladder network of capacitances

I. INTRODUCTION

The accumulation of charges within clouds during thunderstorms and the discharge of these clouds can be represented by the global electrical circuit in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Global electrical circuit with thunderstorm cell (adapted from [1])

Typical approximations for the positive and negative first return stroke currents (*pFS*, *nFS*) and the negative subsequent

return stroke current (*nSS*) are in the form of (multi) exponential, time-continuous functions, which aim to describe the time course of the currents, as shown in Fig. 2, for example.

Fig. 2: Initial courses of negative lightning first short stroke currents measured on extra-high-voltage transmission line towers (adapted from [2], for similar waveshape see also [3], [4])

Most notably is the HEIDLER time function:

$$i(t) = \frac{i_{max}}{\eta} \cdot \frac{e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}}}{1 + \left(\frac{\tau_1}{t}\right)^m} \quad t \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

with which lightning short stroke currents, especially in terms of lightning protection levels (LPL), can be described. The parameters are:

- $i(t)$ - short stroke current; i_{max} - current peak value;
- τ_1 - front time constant; τ_2 - tail time constant;
- m - exponent in lightning pulse current function according to HEIDLER (typically $m = 10$);
- η - crest (peak) factor; t_{imax} - instant of current peak;
- T_1 - front time; T_2 - time to half value in tail;
- T_1/T_2 - time parameters of the current pulse (in μs).

The front of the lightning short stroke currents results in:

$$S_{avg} = \left(\frac{di(t)}{dt} \right)_{front,avg} = \frac{i_{max}}{T_1} \quad (2)$$

$$S_{max} = \left(\frac{di(t)}{dt} \right)_{front,max} \quad (3)$$

S_{avg} – average front steepness (rate of rise of lightning short / return stroke current);

S_{max} – maximum front steepness.

Tab. I gives the known time parameters, front steepness of the pulse and peak values of the short stroke currents according to LPL I [5].

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF STANDARD LIGHTNING SHORT STROKE CURRENT PULSES [5]

Lightning short stroke current	T_1/T_2 $\mu\text{s}/\mu\text{s}$	i_{max} kA	S_{avg} kA/ μs	τ_1 μs	τ_2 μs	η	S_{max} kA/ μs	t_{max} μs
<i>pFS</i>	10/350	200	20	18.8	480	0.937	27.5	31.02
<i>nFS</i>	1/200	100	100	1.826	285	0.988	139	3.563
<i>nSS</i>	0.25/100	50	200	0.454	143.4	0.993	279	0.945

However, with time continuous functions, the discontinuous physical processes during the leader growth phase of the lightning discharge are oversimplified.

So, the aim here is to derive the current course over time for the (negative or positive) first short stroke from the physical potentials and electric field strengths, which are mapped in equivalent circuit diagrams with lumped elements and (charging) voltages. For this purpose, simplified equivalent circuit diagrams are used, that consist only of capacitances and resistances to model the downward (and upward) leader propagation prior to the full lightning stroke.

This modelling can be used for analytical, discontinuous or continuous calculations, as well as for numerical network simulations. This allows to reproduce fairly well the temporal initial or frontal course of the first lightning impulse currents, with initially slow current rise and then high steepness up to the current peak in relation to measured lightning currents, e.g. in Fig. 2.

II. CIRCUIT MODELLING OF LEADER GROWTH PROCESS

A. Circuit Extraction

From the many known models of the global electrical circuit (Fig. 1), the part with the charge center and lightning flash in a thunderstorm is extracted. To simulate the generation of lightning first short stroke currents, an electrical network is used, which essentially consists of series-connected capacitors and ohmic resistors, as shown in Fig. 3.

All capacitors are charged to a high voltage with an equivalent charge quantity before the discharge process, in which the time characteristic of the first short stroke current is to be formed. A fixed capacitance C_0 represents the charge $Q_0 = U_0 \cdot C_0$ accumulated in a charge center, which will be discharged. The partial capacitances C_1 or $C(t)$ represent a small cross-section and length of the later discharge channel within and below the thundercloud. They are charged to their representative portion of the later discharge channel length (U_1 or U_0). The transient process starts and a current begins to flow when either the partial capacitances C_1 are gradually replaced by the lightning discharge channel by short-circuiting C_1 or when a single time-controlled capacitance $C(t)$ in the single-mesh circuit begins to increase steadily. The ohmic effective resistances in the circuit are used to map time constants that

determine the waveform of the current. The fixed resistance R_0 is responsible for the purely exponential discharge in a long tail of the current pulse and essentially determines the peak value i_{max} of the first short stroke current. The partial resistances $R_1 \ll R_0$, which are connected one after the other in the circuit, and likewise the resistance $R(t)$, which increases steadily as time progresses, represent the losses (resistance or voltage build-up) of the developing plasma channel and also determine the current curve of the pulse front and marginally the peak value i_{max} . For simplification, the partial resistances R_1 or the time-controlled resistance $R(t)$ can be omitted.

Fig. 3: Simplified network model with capacitances and resistances and switches for stepped downward leader (left) as well as simplified network model with time-varying capacitance and resistance for continuously developing downward leader (right) and return stroke discharge

B. Circuit Parameters for Negative First Short Stroke

Parameters of the lumped network elements were derived with simple consideration of the following values:

- Starting height for stepped downward leader $H = 5000\text{ m}$; number of jerk steps $n = 50$; mean step length $\bar{l} = H/n = 100\text{ m}$;
- Charging voltage of discharge capacitance and the same for the chain of capacitance in series $U_0 = 100\text{ MV}$;
- Fixed discharge resistance $R_0 = 1\text{ k}\Omega$, $i_{max0} = U_0/R_0 = 100\text{ kA}$;
- Fixed discharge capacitance $C_0 = 287\text{ nF}$, $Q_0 = U_0 \cdot C_0 = 28.7\text{ C}$;
- Series capacitance in total $C_{tot} = 0.5\text{ nF}$, $C_1 = n \cdot C_{tot} = 25\text{ nF}$, $U_1 = U_0/n = 2\text{ MV}$, $C' = C_{tot} \cdot H = 2500\text{ nF} \cdot \text{m}$;
- Voltage gradient of plasma channel $u' = 2\text{ kV/m}$; series resistance in total (represents plasma channel) $R_{tot} = u' \cdot H/i_{max} = 100\Omega$, $R_1 = R_{tot}/n = 2\Omega$, $R' = R_{tot}/H = 0.02\Omega/\text{m}$;
- Waveform of first negative return stroke current $T_1/T_2 = 1/200\mu\text{s}$ with $T_1 = 1\mu\text{s}$ and $T_2 = 200\mu\text{s}$, $T_2 - T_1 \approx \tau \cdot \ln(2)$; time constant of tail $\tau = C_0 \cdot R_0 = 287\mu\text{s}$;

- Peak value of first negative short stroke current $i_{max} = 100\text{kA}$ (LPL I [5]); $i_{max1} = 100.15\text{kA}$ (without R_1, R_{tot}); $i_{max2} = 91.04\text{kA}$ (with R_1, R_{tot}).

The unit-step function $s(t)$ or $s(t - k \cdot T_1)$ is required for the following analytical descriptions ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$):

$$s(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < 0 \\ 1/2 & t = 0 \\ 1 & t > 0 \end{cases} \text{ or } s(t - k \cdot T_1) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < k \cdot T_1 \\ 1/2 & t = k \cdot T_1 \\ 1 & t > k \cdot T_1 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

If stepwise pre-growth of the downward leader is considered (including final jump by upward connecting leader), the equivalent circuit diagram according to Fig. 3 (left) can be used as basis. The following describing equations can be set up in the time domain:

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= n \cdot C_{tot} & R_1 &= R_{tot}/n & \Delta t &= T_1 n \\ u_{C0}(t) &= R_0 \cdot i_1(t) + 1 \cdot R_1 \cdot i_1(t) + (n-1) \cdot u_{C1}(t) \\ \frac{du_{C0}(t)}{dt} &= (R_0 + 1 \cdot R_1) \cdot \frac{di_1(t)}{dt} + (n-1) \cdot \frac{du_{C1}(t)}{dt} \\ i_1(t) &= -C_0 \cdot \frac{du_{C0}(t)}{dt} & i_1(t) &= C_1 \cdot \frac{du_{C1}(t)}{dt} \\ -\frac{i_1(t)}{C_0} &= (R_0 + 1 \cdot R_1) \cdot \frac{di_1(t)}{dt} + (n-1) \cdot \frac{i_1(t)}{C_1} \\ i_1(t) &= -\tau_1 \cdot \frac{di_1(t)}{dt} & i_1(0) &= \frac{U_0}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{R_0 + 1 \cdot R_1} \\ \tau_1 &= \frac{R_0 + 1 \cdot R_1}{\frac{1}{C_0} + (n-1) \cdot \frac{1}{C_1}} & i_1(t) &= s(t) \cdot i_1(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} \end{aligned}$$

Solution for stepped current with series resistances R_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} i_k(t) &= \{s(t - k \cdot \Delta t) - s(t - (k+1) \cdot \Delta t)\} \cdot i_k(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t-k\Delta t}{\tau_k}} \\ \tau_k &= \frac{R_0 + k \cdot R_1}{\frac{1}{C_0} + (n-k) \cdot \frac{1}{C_1}} & i_k(0) &= \frac{u_{C0k} - u_{Cn-k}}{R_0 + k \cdot R_1} & i_0(0) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_{C0k} &= u_{C0k-1} - \frac{1}{C_0} \cdot \int_0^{\Delta t} i_{k-1}(t) dt = U_0 - \frac{1}{C_0} \sum_{j=1}^k \int_0^{\Delta t} i_{j-1}(t) dt \\ &= U_0 - \frac{1}{C_0} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k \tau_{j-1} \cdot i_{j-1}(0) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_{j-1}}}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_{Cn-k} &= \left(u_{Cn-k+1} + \frac{n-k+1}{C_1} \int_0^{\Delta t} i_{k-1}(t) dt\right) \cdot \frac{n-k}{n-k+1} \\ &= (n-k) \cdot \left(\frac{U_0}{n} + \frac{1}{C_1} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k \int_0^{\Delta t} i_{j-1}(t) dt\right) \\ &= (n-k) \cdot \left(\frac{U_0}{n} + \frac{1}{C_1} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k \tau_{j-1} \cdot i_{j-1}(0) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_{j-1}}}\right)\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_k(0) &= \frac{1}{R_0 + k \cdot R_1} \cdot \left[\frac{k}{n} \cdot U_0 - \left(\frac{1}{C_0} + \frac{n-k}{C_1}\right) \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k \tau_{j-1} \cdot i_{j-1}(0) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_{j-1}}}\right)\right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i(t) &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left[\{s(t - k \cdot \Delta t) - s(t - (k+1) \cdot \Delta t)\} \cdot i_k(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t-k\Delta t}{\tau_k}} \right] + s(t - n \cdot \Delta t) \cdot i_n(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t-n\Delta t}{\tau_n}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\tau_n = (R_0 + n \cdot R_1) \cdot C_0 \quad i_n(0) = \frac{U_0}{R_0 + n \cdot R_1}$$

Solution for stepped current without series resistances, $R_1 = R_{tot} = 0$:

$$i_1(0) = \frac{U_0}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{R_0} \quad \tau_1 = \frac{R_0}{\frac{1}{C_0} + (n-1) \cdot \frac{1}{C_1}} \quad \tau_k = \frac{R_0}{\frac{1}{C_0} + (n-k) \cdot \frac{1}{C_1}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i_k(0) &= \frac{1}{R_0} \cdot \left[\frac{k}{n} \cdot U_0 - \left(\frac{1}{C_0} + \frac{n-k}{C_1}\right) \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k \tau_{j-1} \cdot i_{j-1}(0) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_{j-1}}}\right)\right] \end{aligned}$$

$$i_k(t) = \{s(t - k \cdot \Delta t) - s(t - (k+1) \cdot \Delta t)\} \cdot i_k(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t-k\Delta t}{\tau_k}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} i(t) &= \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left[\{s(t - k \cdot \Delta t) - s(t - (k+1) \cdot \Delta t)\} \cdot i_k(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t-k\Delta t}{\tau_k}} \right] + s(t - n \cdot \Delta t) \cdot i_n(0) \cdot e^{-\frac{t-n\Delta t}{\tau_n}} \\ \tau_n &= R_0 \cdot C_0 \quad i_n(0) = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \end{aligned}$$

The initial time courses for the pulse current as an exemplary result are shown in Fig. 4, where the parameters $n = 50$, $U_0 = 100\text{MV}$, $C_0 = 287\text{nF}$, $R_0 = 1\text{k}\Omega$, $C_{tot} = 0.5\text{nF}$, $C_1 = 25\text{nF}$, $R_{tot} = 100\Omega$, $R_1 = 2\Omega$, $T_1 = 1\mu\text{s}$, $\Delta t = 20\text{ns}$ were used. The fine stepped course of the pulse front is clearly visible. The beginning of the pulse tail in Fig. 4 (right-hand end) indicates a slow exponential decay down to zero current.

Fig. 4: Front part of lightning short stroke current pulses for stepped and continuous downward leader development

To better illustrate the stepped behavior of the downward leader in the leader current (front part of the unipolar pulse), very few steps and a smaller total capacitance ($C_{tot}^* = C_{tot}/2$) are assumed in leader development: $n = 10$, $U_0 = 100\text{MV}$, $C_0 = 287\text{nF}$, $R_0 = 1\text{k}\Omega$, $C_{tot}^* = 0.01\text{nF}$, $C_1^* = 0.1\text{nF}$, $R_{tot} = 100\Omega$, $R_1 = 10\Omega$, $T_1 = 1\mu\text{s}$, $\Delta t = 100\text{ns}$ (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Front part of lightning short stroke current pulses for stepped downward leader development with 10 steps only and at reduced total capacitance compared again to continuous front of current pulses

Fig. 5 shows the current spikes when each partial capacitance is short-circuited (formation of a new jerk stage of the downward leader) and the exponential decay of the current afterwards. This exponential decay reaches less and less zero current as time progresses.

III. CONTINUOUS FRONT OF PULSE CURRENT

If the number n of jerk steps is very large and the step time Δt is very small, then a quasi-continuous course of the pulse front occurs. Corresponding continuous front shapes are already shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 for comparison. The equations for analytical calculation with continuous increase of capacitance $C(t)$ and resistance $R(t)$ are derived below:

$$t = 0 \dots T_1 \quad C(t) = \frac{C_{tot}}{1 - \frac{t}{T_1}} \quad C = C_{tot} \dots \infty$$

$$t = 0 \dots T_1 \quad R(t) = R_{tot} \cdot \frac{t}{T_1} \quad R = 0 \dots R_{tot}$$

The solution for current $i(t)$ is deduced from a system of two non-linear differential equations with initial conditions by applying with and without continuously time-varying series resistance:

$$i(t) = R_0 \cdot C_0 \cdot \frac{di(t)}{dt} + C_0 \cdot \frac{d u_C(t)}{dt} + R_{tot} \cdot C_0 \cdot \frac{1}{T_1} \cdot \left(i(t) + t \cdot \frac{di(t)}{dt} \right)$$

$$i(t) = \frac{C_{tot}}{1 - \frac{t}{T_1}} \cdot \left(\frac{u_C(t)}{T_1 - t} + \frac{d u_C(t)}{dt} \right) \quad i(0) = 0 \quad u_C(0) = U_0$$

Solution for continuous current with series resistance $R(t)$:

$$\text{gamma function } \Gamma(a, z) = \int_z^\infty e^{-x} \cdot x^{a-1} dx$$

$$\tau_0 = C_0 \cdot R_0 \quad \tau_{tot} = C_{tot} \cdot R_{tot} \quad \tau_{tot0} = C_0 \cdot R_{tot} \quad \tau_{tot0} = C_{tot} \cdot R_0$$

$$c = \frac{R_0}{R_{tot}} \cdot \frac{T_1}{\tau_{tot}} \quad d = T_1 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\tau_{tot}} - \frac{1}{\tau_{tot0}} \right) - c$$

$$i(t) = [s(t) - s(t - T_1)] \cdot \frac{U_0}{\tau_0 + \tau_{tot0} - \tau_{tot}} \cdot \left[e^{c + \frac{t}{\tau_{tot}}} \cdot \left((t - T_1) \cdot C_0 + C_{tot} \cdot T_1 \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\tau_{tot}} - \frac{1}{\tau_{tot0}} \right) \cdot \left(\Gamma(1 + d, c) - \Gamma\left(1 + d, c + \frac{t}{\tau_{tot}}\right) \right) \cdot \left(c + \frac{t}{\tau_{tot}} \right)^{-(1+d)} + c^d \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{tot}}} \cdot \frac{(t - T_1) \cdot \tau_0 + T_1 \cdot \tau_{tot0}}{R_0 \cdot T_1 + R_{tot} \cdot t} \cdot \left(c + \frac{t}{\tau_{tot}} \right)^{-d} + C_0 - C_{tot} \right] + s(t - T_1) \cdot i_{max} \cdot e^{-\frac{t - T_1}{\tau_0 + \tau_{tot0}}}$$

$$i_{max} = i(T_1) = \frac{U_0}{\tau_0 + \tau_{tot0} - \tau_{tot}} \cdot \left[e^{c + \frac{T_1}{\tau_{tot}}} \cdot \frac{T_1}{R_{tot}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \cdot \left(\Gamma(1 + d, c) - \Gamma\left(1 + d, c + \frac{T_1}{\tau_{tot}}\right) \right) \cdot \left(c + \frac{T_1}{\tau_{tot}} \right)^{-(1+d)} + c^d \cdot e^{-\frac{T_1}{\tau_{tot}}} \cdot \frac{\tau_{tot0}}{R_{tot} + R_0} \cdot \left(c + \frac{T_1}{\tau_{tot}} \right)^{-d} + C_0 - C_{tot} \right]$$

Solution for continuous current without series resistance, $R_{tot} = R(t) = 0$:

$$\text{error function } \text{erf}(z) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \int_0^z e^{-x^2} dx$$

$$\tau_0 = C_0 \cdot R_0 \quad \tau_{tot0} = C_{tot} \cdot R_0 \quad d = \sqrt{2 \cdot \tau_{tot0} \cdot T_1}$$

$$i(t) = [s(t) - s(t - T_1)] \cdot \frac{U_0}{\tau_0 \cdot d} \cdot \left[\left[\frac{d}{T_1} + \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{T_1}{d} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \right) \cdot e^{\frac{T_1^2}{d^2} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right)^2} \right] \cdot e^{t \cdot \left(\frac{1}{d^2} - \frac{1}{\tau_{tot0}} + \frac{1}{\tau_0} \right)} \cdot \left((t - T_1) \cdot C_0 + T_1 \cdot C_{tot} \right) + \left[\sqrt{\pi} \cdot \left((t - T_1) \cdot C_0 + T_1 \cdot C_{tot} \right) \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{t - T_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right)}{d} \right) \cdot e^{\frac{(t - T_1) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right)^2}{d^2}} + C_0 \cdot d \right] \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \right] + s(t - T_1) \cdot i_{max} \cdot e^{-\frac{t - T_1}{\tau_0}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
i_{max} = i(T_1) = & \frac{U_0}{\tau_0 \cdot d} \cdot \left(\left[\frac{d}{T_1} + \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \right. \right. \\
& \cdot \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{T_1}{d} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \right) \cdot e^{\frac{T_1^2}{d^2} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right)^2} \left. \left. \right] \right. \\
& \cdot T_1 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\tau_0} - \frac{1}{2\tau_{tot0}} \right) \cdot T_1 \cdot C_{tot} \\
& + \left[\sqrt{\pi} \cdot T_1 \cdot C_{tot} \cdot \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{T_1}{d} \cdot \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \cdot e^{\left(\frac{T_1}{d} \cdot \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right)^2} \right. \\
& \left. \left. + C_0 \cdot d \right] \cdot \left(1 - \frac{C_{tot}}{C_0} \right) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

The parameters $U_0 = 100 \text{ MV}$, $C_0 = 287 \text{ nF}$, $R_0 = 1 \text{ k}\Omega$, $C_{tot} = 0.5 \text{ nF}$, $R_{tot} = 100 \Omega$, $T_1 = 1 \mu\text{s} \rightarrow i_{max} = 91.04 \text{ kA}$ were used for continuous current with time-varying series resistance, and $U_0 = 100 \text{ MV}$, $C_0 = 287 \text{ nF}$, $R_0 = 1 \text{ k}\Omega$, $C_{tot} = 0.5 \text{ nF}$, $R_{tot} = 0 \Omega$, $T_1 = 1 \mu\text{s} \rightarrow i_{max} = 100.15 \text{ kA}$ were used for continuous current without time-varying series resistance. The initial courses are shown in Fig. 4 or Fig. 5, the time courses up to half-value in the tail can be seen in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Lightning short stroke current pulses for continuous downward leader development over time up to half of peak value in tail

The pulse front shows a curved course, on average the current rises in an s-shaped course. The pulse tail is characterized by purely exponential decay after the peak.

IV. TIME FUNCTION WITH UPWARD LEADER SPEED

A similar lightning current function can be derived if an average velocity v is assumed for the development of the upward leader from the ground to the downward leader tip. The temporal pulse current course can in turn be developed from a simplified consideration of the channel formation.

The pre-growth of the upward leader discharge might be imagined as continuous short-circuiting of partial capacitances connected in series between the earth and the lower downward leader tip. With each such partial discharge, a small displacement current flows and, at the same time, the effective capacitance between the upward leader tip and the downward leader tip increases (Fig. 7).

The lightning discharge is to be fed by a fixed capacitance C_0 which is charged to the voltage U_0 at start time of the upward leader. There is an ohmic resistor R_0 in series with this capacitance, which limits the discharge current. At the start of the upward leader, the effective capacitance between

Fig. 7: Simplified capacitive circuit of developing upward leader in steps by short-circuiting of partial capacitances and therefore stepwise elevating of capacitance ground to downward leader tip

the earth and the downward leader tip is also charged up to voltage U_0 .

If one assumes a continuous upward growth of the upward leader at constant speed v and thus a continuous increase in effective capacitance, then one obtains a continuous increase in the capacitive displacement current.

To derive the current time course up to the point where the two leader channels meet, Kirchhoff's voltage law can be set up using Fig. 7:

$$\frac{1}{C_0} \cdot \int i(t) dt + R_0 \cdot i(t) + u_z(t) = 0 \quad (5)$$

Considering the time-varying capacitance C_z , the current-voltage relationship is as follows:

$$i(t) = \frac{d(C_z(t) \cdot u_z(t))}{dt} = u_z(t) \cdot \frac{dC_z(t)}{dt} + C_z(t) \cdot \frac{du_z(t)}{dt} \quad (6)$$

The time-varying capacitance C_z and its time derivative can be used here if a length-related capacitance C' is assumed for the series connection:

$$C_z(t) = \frac{C'}{\ell - v \cdot t} \quad \frac{dC_z(t)}{dt} = \frac{v \cdot C'}{(\ell - v \cdot t)^2} \quad (7)$$

Whereby $C_z(0) = C'/\ell$ is the effective capacitance at the downward leader tip at time $t = 0$, at which the upward leader is to be launched. If the equations (7) are inserted into the relationship (6) and the resulting differential equation is solved for $u_z(t)$, the result is:

$$u_z(t) = \frac{\ell - v \cdot t}{C'} \cdot \left[\int i(t) dt + K \right] \quad (8)$$

This relationship (8) can be substituted into Kirchhoff's voltage law (5). After double differentiation to eliminate the time integrals and normalization of the expression, a special

2nd order non-linear differential equation is obtained for the discharge current $i(t)$:

$$\frac{d^2 i(t)}{dt^2} + \frac{1}{R_0} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{C_0} + \frac{\ell - v \cdot t}{C'} \right) \cdot \frac{di(t)}{dt} - \frac{2}{R_0} \cdot \frac{v}{C'} \cdot i(t) = 0 \quad (9)$$

The initial conditions for the specific solution are:

$$i(0) = 0 \quad \left. \frac{di(t)}{dt} \right|_{t=0} = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \cdot \frac{v}{\ell} \neq 0 \quad (10)$$

The current rise at $t = 0$ is not the lowest in the front of the current course. The lowest current rise occurs shortly after the start of the current flow.

For better handling, two abbreviated length parameters are introduced:

$$A = \frac{C'}{C_0} + \ell \quad B = \sqrt{2 \cdot C' \cdot R_0 \cdot v} \quad A, B \text{ in m}$$

The discharge time t_{max} up to current peak results from the discharge length ℓ and the constant pre-growing speed v :

$$t_{max} = \frac{A}{v} \gtrsim \frac{\ell}{v} \quad t_{max} \sim \ell \quad t_{max} \sim \frac{1}{v} \quad (11)$$

The solution of the differential equation (9) states:

$$i(t) = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \cdot \frac{1}{\ell} \cdot \left[\frac{A - (A - v \cdot t) \cdot e^{-\frac{v}{B^2} \cdot (2 \cdot A - v \cdot t)}}{\sqrt{\pi} \cdot \frac{A}{B} \cdot (A - v \cdot t) \cdot e^{\left(\frac{A - v \cdot t}{B}\right)^2}} + \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{A - v \cdot t}{B}\right) - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{A}{B}\right) \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) again contains the error function $\operatorname{erf}(z)$. The current value at low-resistive (low-impedance) closure of the plasma channel (upward leader meets downward leader), which here also marks the peak of the current course i_{max} , is:

$$i_{max} = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \cdot \frac{A}{\ell} \gtrsim \frac{U_0}{R_0} \quad i_{max} \sim U_0 \quad (13)$$

The smallest average current steepness is:

$$S_{avg}^* = \frac{i_{max}}{t_{max}} = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \cdot \frac{v}{\ell} \quad S_{avg}^* \sim \frac{U_0}{\ell} \quad S_{avg}^* \sim v \quad (14)$$

The largest (maximum) current steepness S_{max} occurs directly at (before) t_{max} (pulse peak).

$$\left. \frac{di(t)}{dt} \right|_{t_{max}} = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \cdot \frac{1}{\ell} \cdot \left[\begin{aligned} & \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2}{B^2} \cdot (A - v \cdot t)^2 \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{v}{B^2} \cdot (2 \cdot A - v \cdot t)} \\ & - v \cdot A \cdot \frac{2}{B^2} \cdot (A - v \cdot t) - \\ & v \cdot (1 + 2 \cdot (A - v \cdot t)) \cdot \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \frac{A}{B} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{A - v \cdot t}{B}\right)^2} \\ & \cdot \left(\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{A - v \cdot t}{B}\right) - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{A}{B}\right) \right) \end{aligned} \right]$$

This results in the maximum current steepness:

$$S_{max} = \left. \frac{di(t)}{dt} \right|_{t_{max}} = \frac{U_0}{R_0} \cdot \frac{v}{\ell} \cdot \left[e^{-\left(\frac{A}{B}\right)^2} + \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \frac{A}{B} \cdot \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{A}{B}\right) \right]$$

After current peak or after t_{max} , only the fixed capacitance C_0 is discharged over R_0 :

$$i(t) = i_{max} \cdot e^{-\frac{t - t_{max}}{C_0 R_0}} \quad \text{for } t > t_{max} \quad (15)$$

The following values may be assumed for detailed calculation:

- Height of downward leader tip above ground when the upward leader starts $\ell = 30 \text{ m}$ (for stepwise representation $n = 100$ is the number of steps, step length $\ell/n = 0.3 \text{ m}$);
- Mean velocity of upward leader $v = 1/100 \cdot c = 3 \times 10^6 \text{ m/s} = 3 \text{ m}/\mu\text{s} \rightarrow t_{max} \approx \ell/v = 10 \mu\text{s}$;
- Assumption of length-related capacitance $C' = 3 \text{ nF} \cdot \text{m} \rightarrow C_z(0) = C'/\ell = 0.1 \text{ nF}$;
- $C_0 = 0.2 \mu\text{F}$ $U_0 = 30 \text{ MV} \rightarrow Q_0 = C_0 \cdot U_0 = 6 \text{ C}$
 $\rightarrow E_m = U_0/\ell = 1 \text{ MV/m} = 10 \text{ kV/cm}$ (average electric field strength at start of upward leader);
- $R_0 = 1 \text{ k}\Omega$ (assumption for peak value and decay)
 $\rightarrow i_{max} = i(t_{max}) \approx U_0/R_0 = 30 \text{ kA}$ ($i_{max} = 29.83 \text{ kA}$)
 $\rightarrow \tau_0 = C_0 \cdot R_0 = 200 \mu\text{s}$ (time constant for tail)
 $\rightarrow di/dt|_{t=0} = U_0/R_0 \cdot v/\ell = 3 \times 10^9 \text{ A/s} = 3 \text{ kA}/\mu\text{s}$
 $\rightarrow di/dt|_{t=t_{max}} = 3.732 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/s} \approx 37 \text{ kA}/\mu\text{s}$ (maximum front steepness of pulse current).

These parameters were used for the calculation of continuous current with time-varying series capacitance in Fig. 8. The

Fig. 8: Example of discharge current over time derived with upward leader speed (comparison with discontinuous discharge for many steps)

plots in Fig. 8 show the lightning first short stroke current with comparatively long front time ($\sim 10/350 \mu\text{s}$, pFS), whereby a discontinuous front part with many steps was also added.

V. NETWORK CIRCUITS FOR TRANSIENT SIMULATION

The numerical calculation of lightning impulse current courses can also be carried out very favourably using network analysis software tools, e.g. ATP/EMTP for transient simulation in time domain [6]. The use of many (ideal) on (and off) switches (possibly voltage-controlled switches) is generally easy to implement in such programs. In a few program systems, time-dependent/time-controlled capacitance and resistance (and inductance) are also available.

For the stepwise development of the downward or upward leader, the partial capacitances can be short-circuited one after the other with switches. The switches can be closed with predefined switch-on times (e.g. equidistant time lag) or they can switch automatically when defined voltage values are exceeded at the partial capacitances (air breakdown).

The circuit diagrams in Fig. 9 show examples of the implementation in ATPDraw [7], whereby the connection of other network parts in which the lightning impulse current is to be injected is of course conceivable.

Fig. 9: Examples of capacitive ladder circuits for numerical calculation of lightning short stroke currents; $R_1 - C_1$ -ladder with ideal switches (left); C_1 -ladder with dependent time-controlled switches (middle); C_1 -ladder with voltage-controlled switches (right)

In addition, the simulation with stepwise switch-on of parallel capacitances can be used, which must have a nonlinearly decreasing initial voltage.

Note: The controlled (time-dependent) capacitance (TACS controlled capacitor) available in ATP cannot be used here, because the continuous "short-circuiting", i.e. the neutralization of charge, is not emulated in this model. However, any increase in the capacitance value over time can be programmed, but by default no initial voltage can be set for the controlled capacitance.

For the elongated (plasma) discharge channel, one single inductance can be added in the network model or, in the (stepwise) downward leader development, inductances L_1 (in series with the resistors R_1) or one continuously increasing inductance $L(t)$ (in series with the resistor $R(t)$, R') may be added.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Depending on the level of detail required for the application, there are different approaches to model lightning discharges for 0D-network calculations. Most notably are commonly accepted time-continuous equations (e.g. HEIDLER-function) which represent the discharge as current source. However, the level of physical abstraction for these types of equation-based models is quite high, especially in the pre-strike phase of the discharge. So, for applications, where the pre-strike current is of particular interest, an extended model is presented here.

With the help of equivalent circuit diagrams consisting of one fixed charged capacitance in series with one damping resistor and a stepwise or continuously increasing capacitance that is also charged, it was possible to derive discontinuous

or continuous current-time functions for the front of lightning first short strokes. Supplemented with an exponentially decaying tail, the continuous pulse current course is summarized and generalized to ($t_{max} \cong T_1$, $\tau_0 \cong T_2/\ln(2) \approx 1.44 \cdot T_2$, $e \cdot \text{erf}(1) = 2.29$):

$$i(t) \cong i_{max} \cdot \begin{cases} \frac{t}{2.29 \cdot t_{max}} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{t}{t_{max}}\right)^2} \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{t}{t_{max}}\right) & 0 \leq t < t_{max} \\ e^{-\frac{t-t_{max}}{\tau_0}} & t \geq t_{max} \end{cases}$$

In this way, the concave front known from measured lightning short stroke currents is reproduced quite effectively. Moreover, the pulse-shaped character of the displacement current during the formation of the individual jerk stages of the downward leader can also be described by sudden stepwise increase of capacitance via successive short-circuiting of serial partial capacitances.

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